

CULTURE IS A CERTAIN LEVEL OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY, HUMAN CREATIVE POWER AND ABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Culture is a set of symbolic devices and works that define human activity and the importance of this activity. Culture can be manifested in activities such as music, literature, visual arts, architecture, theater, cinematography, and lifestyle. In anthropology, the term “culture” refers to products and their production, aesthetic meaning, and social relations connected to these processes. In this sense, culture includes art, science, and spiritual systems. Culture is a certain level of historical development of society, human creative power and abilities. It is expressed in various forms of people’s life and activities, as well as in the material and spiritual wealth they create. The concept of culture is used to explain a specific historical period (ancient culture), concrete society, people and nation, as well as specific areas of human activity or life. In a narrow sense, the term culture is used only in the sphere of the spiritual life of people. Culture comes from the Arabic word madina (city). Arabs divide people’s lives into two types: one is Bedouin or desert life; the second is called cultural life. Bedouins are nomadic peoples living in the steppes and deserts, culturalism is used for peoples who live in cities and have their own way of life.

Keywords: *society, human, artistic culture, life, theories and ideas, cinema, theater scenes, museums and exhibition halls, nature, management, spheres, banks, companies, firms, construction organizations, travel agencies, transport institutions.*

“CULTURE IS A CERTAIN LEVEL OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY, HUMAN CREATIVE POWER INTRODUCTION In AND ABILITIES”

The concept of culture is applied to many views, theories and ideas, concepts and imaginations that determine the interaction between nature, society and people. Culture is a certain level of historical development of society, human creative power and abilities, and it is expressed in various aspects of people's lives and activities, as well as in the material and spiritual wealth they create. The concept of culture is a specific historical period (ancient culture), concrete society, nation and nation (Uzbek culture), as well as specific areas of human activity or life (artistic culture, life culture) is used to explain. Currently, there are more than 400 definitions of the term "culture". If we pay attention to them, we will see that the concept of culture covers almost all and even contradictory spheres of life, and therefore are very difficult to define the concept of culture. If we look at the literature on cultural studies, we can see that there are different definitions and interpretations of culture, such as: "the sum of material and spiritual wealth created by man"; "material and spiritual values"; "second nature created by man"; "product of human activity"; "creative activity"; "product of creative activity"; "spiritual life of society"; "spiritual world of man"; "moral qualities of a person"; "inner and outer world of man"; "sum of moral qualities"; "community activities"; "summary of the conditional symbol system"; "conditional images"; "symbolic signs and symbols"; "norms and standards" and so on. We see that "madaniyat" is derived from the Arabic word "madina" and means "city". Arabs divide people's lives into two types: one is Bedouin or desert life; the second is called cultural life. Bedouins are nomadic peoples who live in the steppe deserts, and cultural peoples are peoples who live in cities and have their own way of life. In Europe, the word "culture" originally meant the purposeful influence of man on nature, as well as education (Lat. cultura - tillage, maintenance; the word "culture" in Russian is derived from it). The incomparable changes in human society, the increasing complexity of economic-political and socio-cultural relations between states and regions, fundamental changes in the economic and spiritual life of society, the emergence of human potential, the interaction of nature and society. The need for generalizing concepts about the evolution of life, nature, society, human thinking, development, people's life, and

mutual relations led to a change in the essence of the concept of culture. The great thinkers of Central Asia approach the issue of civilization from the point of view of a person's mental and spiritual maturity, the development of consciousness and thinking, the issue of a virtuous society and perfect people. Eastern thinkers such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Beruni, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Imam Ghazali, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi understand the issue of culture in the form of spiritual and mental perfection of a person, in the way of achieving happiness. This traditional concept has a strong place in the thinking of the next generations. For this reason, when we say "culture", we mean the spirituality of a person, his internal experiences and the commonality of his external appearance. The culture of a particular nation is first determined by the specific aspects, characteristics, and interrelationships of the material and spiritual activities of this nation created in each social and historical period. The process of creation of all material and spiritual wealth by mankind is considered to be a continuous process from the bottom up, from the simple to the complex, from the individual to the general, and there is a dialectical unity between its past and present appearance. All stages in the process of creation of cultural wealth have always complemented each other. But the culture created at a certain stage of human history differs from the culture created at previous stages and comes into being in a changed state. The society does not blindly accept the cultural wealth of its predecessors, but changes them in a positive way. Culture is created according to the needs of each era. If we pay attention to the issue of the interaction of material and spiritual culture, we can see that the elements of material culture were first created by mankind, and then more complex types appeared that combined several elements of material culture and performed different tasks. Let's see if it is.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The concept of culture has broad and narrow meanings. The concept of culture in a broad sense includes all material and spiritual wealth created as a result of the practical activities of all people. Culture is a set of all the riches created in the course

of the socio-historical experience of humanity, that is, in the process of work aimed at changing nature and society.

The concept of culture in a narrow sense is used in relation to all areas that cover the sphere of human spiritual life. Culture is considered, firstly, in the form of consumer goods that satisfy the biological and social needs of a person, and secondly, as a product of production activities and is divided into two types: material and spiritual culture. Material culture is, first of all, labor tools, transport, means of communication, housing, clothing, food, various goods, in short, all things that satisfy the material needs of mankind, as well as the production experiences, skills and abilities of people. Spiritual culture is people's knowledge, experiences, traditions, behavior, science, literature, art, philosophy, morality, law, scientific outlook, religious beliefs, education, press, in short, are all spiritual riches that satisfy the spiritual needs of mankind. In the course of its development, culture is also divided into some sectors. One of these is management culture.

The role of management in the life of society is incomparable. In the economic spheres, banks, companies, firms, construction organizations, travel agencies, transport institutions, in the social sphere, in all spheres such as healthcare, education, information and communication spheres, management functions as a manager. Management activities in the field of culture and art are very different from these fields.

In education or economy, numbers, tables, tables are compared, and in culture and art, the influence of cinema and theater scenes, museums and exhibition halls, concert organizations and art groups, nongovernmental and public organizations on the public spirit his artistic works "speak". This feature has a direct impact on the development of cultural management.

The promotion of culture, the interpretation of its manifestations through works of art that have entered the hearts of the people through the efforts of artists, artists, composers, stage masters, and directors is a proof that this field is an inseparable and integral link in the life of society. ➤ Development of management theory and practice based on changing the forms and methods of economic organization; ➤ The decisive

influence of the external environment on the choice and formation of the organization's management system; ➤ Conformity of the social structure of management with forms of ownership of the organization's property; ➤ The connection between controlling and controlled subsystems (subject and object of control); ➤ Use mainly conscious (planned) management; ➤ Concentration and dynamic change of management functions in the organization; ➤ Optimization (rationalization) of the management level of the organization; ➤ Rational use of management, accounting and analysis functions in management processes

Management principles, i.e. the implementation of management functions, are built on the basis of the main ideas and rules of management.

Goal management is one of the most important methodological foundations of management. The purpose of the organization's activities means waiting for the result of its activities. From this point of view, achieving the goal determines the main activity of the organization. In the process of achieving the expected result, all available resources, including financial and social (employee work) and others, are involved. "From the point of view of management, the goal means the desired state of the object of control after a certain time. To translate a control system from an existing state to a desired state, a specific action program is needed to solve the problem that separates the current state from the desired state."

In order to achieve a specific goal, any organization develops an action program aimed at solving a number of tasks, defines the main means of achieving them, and plans all planned activities in detail. In culture and art institutions, the goal is realized with the help of well-founded, selected strategy and tactics. The aesthetic development of the creative potential of each artist, the formation of personal consciousness, and the recognition of his works serve to realize the goal.

In this regard, an experienced manager should pay attention to a number of aspects, for example: • to be the main idea of the organization's priorities-goal; •

analysis of the accuracy of the goal in comparison with the available resources; • preparation of final conclusions necessary to achieve the goal.

In organizations related to culture and art, as well as the activities of each sector, the official duties of employees are divided according to their responsibilities and labor capacity. In the course of goal setting, planning and implementation, a number of groups operating in several directions are formed.

Well-known experts see organizations operating in the field of culture as examples of three groups:

The first group is cultural heritage (museum and archival collections, folk art), because of their high social value, the importance of preservation for future generations, it cannot be the object of market relations, it includes objects of experimental forms of art takes.

Cultural heritage (museum exhibits, collections, archival materials related to the field of culture and art, masterpieces of folk art, etc.) that must be handed down from ancestors to generations.

The first group, cultural institutions (libraries, information-resource centers) legally guaranteed by state standards of consumer culture of services.

The second group, cultural institutions engaged in commercial directions (legally operating studios, polygraphy, advertising and design promotion) organizations, the third group constitutes.

Depending on the type of activity, the manager should know exactly what to do to work in a museum, theater or exhibition complex, how to solve the organization's problems. In this regard, experts pay attention to the concept of management mechanisms in the field of culture with technological or instrumental presentation. This is reflected in the relative interdependence of goals, functions, and means that allows to achieves specific results. From this point of view, management can be expressed as a system consisting of four main mechanisms: • Organizational and administrative mechanism; • Economic mechanism; • The mechanism of working with employees; • Information mechanism.

When considering management as the work of these four mechanisms, future managers should develop the structure of separate components of management work, each of them should perform the appropriate work. Organizational documents include statutes, regulations, contracts, and job descriptions. Cultural organizations operate on the basis of regulations. To regulate the activities of each employee, job descriptions are developed, which specify the requirements for the employee appointed to the position, the appointment procedure, as well as the rights and the level of responsibility. An addition to the creation of an organizational and administrative mechanism, it is carried out with personnel tables of institutions that regulate the number of positions and official salary amounts. The management of culture and art institutions cannot be reduced to only one mechanism. In this, profitability and efficiency are important as an economic mechanism is a system of incentives (i.e. wages, material incentives, etc.) Today, researchers often emphasize the use of the advantages of the economic mechanism in various methods of administrative practices of the former Soviet era. Work with employees - selection and training of qualified employees, creating opportunities for their systematic training, formation and development of incentives for active work are all the bases of the mechanism of work with employees.

Any management is decision-making, and decision-making is the first step in ensuring the goal and mission of management reports (in the form of audits) are also an important part of the mechanism of working with employees. All this depends on the preparation, acceptance, approval, use and storage of relevant documents. Relationships and interdependence between management decisions, planning, control, accounting and reporting, document circulation and information mechanism.

Full and reasonable functioning of the information mechanism is the basis for the creation of new innovative ideas. As a conclusion of the second chapter, it should be noted that the role of the concept of the manager, personal and work-related qualities, in the effective activity of leaders in the field of culture and art incomparable Also, forming a unique work style of a manager, leader, leader in solving this or that problem,

taking into account the national mentality, constantly analyzing the art market, improving the leader's speech culture, forming the leader's image, scientific and creative processes, today's requirements level of understanding is one of the urgent tasks of the fast time.

CONCLUSION

In short, Material and spiritual cultures exist not only in relation to each other, but also have different aspects that distinguish them from each other. This difference can be seen, first of all, in the fact that spiritual culture exists in two forms - objects and as a product of activity. Books, works of fine and sculptural art, architectural monuments, movies, television, etc. are material manifestations of spiritual culture, that is, in the form of objects. The performance and skills of pedagogues and promoters are products of activity. Material cultural assets wear out over time, are destroyed, damaged, and may disappear without a trace after completing their service. Spiritual and cultural wealth is preserved in the minds and eyes of future generations in the form of national values, even though centuries pass. Their main content: Ideas, principles, norms are passed from generation to generation and will live forever. They help social development in every historical and cultural process. The second difference between material and spiritual cultures is related to human material needs - food, clothing, housing, etc. needs will be somewhat limited. Spiritual needs, i.e. acquiring knowledge, watching or listening to works of art, studying scientific fields, communicating with people, organizing or participating in customs, ceremonies, and other types of mental activity are always needed and increases continuously. Thirdly, another of the differences between material and spiritual culture is that, while material values (material culture) are more intended for consumption, spiritual values (spiritual culture) help to form the human personality, serves for perfection. Fourthly, various elements of material culture are designed to satisfy specific needs.

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